
**COMPARATIVE STUDY OF ACHIEVEMENT MOTIVATION
BETWEEN MALE AND FEMALE SPORT STUDENTS**

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Abstract:

The present study has been designed to investigate the achievement motivation of male and female players. It is inconsistently reported that despite equal cognitive ability, and academic environment male and female Achievement is different. Achievement motivation of the college students is the matter of great concern in the 21st century Indian society. Unless the students have high level of achievement motivation it will be difficult on the part of the society to develop and to be at par with other developed society. Therefore right from the lower level up to the higher level there should be proper emphasis on the development of the desire to attain excellence in all walks of life. As such the present study is an attempt to focus the achievement motivation of the male and female players in Ahmednagar with reference to gender. In several methodological steps, the present study examined the level of achievement motivation, differences in achievement motivation across gender, academic streams and to find out the significant differences in achievement motivation of male and female players. For accomplish the study total 120 (60 male players and 60 female players) players were randomly selected as sample. All samples were selected from Ahmednagar. The age of the subjects was ranged from 16-21 years. Descriptive method of research was employed and data was collected through Deo-Mohan achievement motivation scale. Mean, Std. D, t-test and ANOVA was done through SPSS 21 to determine the achievement motivation of players. Results reported that. For measure the achievement motivation Dr. M.C. Kamlesh questionnaire was used. The obtained data were analysed by applying t test in order. The level of significance was set at 0.05. We find out that male players and female players are not significantly different at achievement motivation.

Keywords: *Achievement Motivation, Female and Male Sport Students.*

Introduction:

The motivation of completion can be defined as the predisposition of the athlete approaches or evidence of a

competitive situation. The motivation of the realization includes the concept of desire or desire for improvement. Motivation is an internal force that speeds

up a response or behaviour. Some people learn the same subject or task more effectively than other people, some find it more enjoyable, rewarding and interesting than others and a value more than others. At the same time people vary in that they are willing to direct their energies towards achieving the goals, due to the difference in motivation. The reason for success comes when a person knows that their performance will be evaluated, as a result of their actions will be a success or a failure and that good performance will produce a sense of pride in the performance. Therefore, the reason for success can be considered as a willingness to address success or ability to rely on successful fulfilment when any activity is achieved. The purpose of the study is to compare the achievement motivation between male and female players. It was also hypothesized that There would be no significant difference in achievement motivation between male and female player. Achievement motive is a concept developed by the social psychologist McClelland to denote the strong urge felt by an individual or society for achievement in various aspects like education, culture, money, etc. that satisfies the need of self-esteem. The achievement motive is the deciding factor in attaining success in different fields. An achieving society is characterized by the

history of a strong and persistent achievement motivation. According to Atkinson and Feather (1966), “Achievement motivation is conceived as a talent disposition which is manifested in overt striving only when the individual perceives performance as instrumental to a sense of personal accomplishment.” Individuals high in achievement motivation are at their best when they can maintain a high level of involvement in ensuring the excellence of activities under their coordination or control. However, they do relatively less well when required to manage excessive tasks or to function in highly stressful environments.

Defining Sports:

A game can be defined as an organized activity where two or more individuals or teams compete to win, according to agreed-on rules (Chick, 1984; Roberts, Arth, & Bush, 1959). A sport can be defined as the subset of games that require physical skill (Deaner & Smith, 2013; see Chick, 1984; Guttman, 2004). This definition of sport therefore excludes noncompetitive physical activities (i.e., exercise), games of pure chance (e.g., roulette), and strategic games that depend solely on mental skill or decision making (e.g., chess).

A Sex Difference in Sports:

Interest Although most scholars recognize that boys and men generally exhibit greater sports interest than girls and women, some dispute this or argue that differences in observed sports behaviour do not represent differences in underlying interest (Brake, 2010; Hogshead-Makar & Zimbalist, 2007). In this section, we demonstrate that there is unambiguous evidence for a substantial sex difference in sports participation and spectatorship. We also review several lines of evidence indicating that these patterns reflect a sex difference in underlying sports interest, not merely differences in opportunities for engagement.

Motivation and Gender:

Students' motivational beliefs in different subjects are guides of students' feelings, actions and thinking that lead them towards success in learning (Clayton, Blumberg & Auld, 2010). Most of the previous researchers found that female students are more motivated towards the achievement of desirable learning goals as compared to male students. But from previously conducted researches it was found that the levels of intrinsic motivation of students vary on different subjects, towards various subjects' different genders have different higher intrinsic and extrinsic motivation. No

significant gender difference in higher motivation was found in all subject areas. In comparing gender differences in different subjects at the university level, a study conducted by Narayanan, Rajasekaran, and Iyyappan (2007) found that in learning English, girls have greater intrinsic motivation compared to boys. Similarly, another research study reported higher intrinsic motivation in physical education among females as compare to males (Shang, 1998). Schatt (2011) found that female students perform better in Instrumental musical practice in the subject of music that significantly correlated with their intrinsic motivational beliefs than males.

Achievement motivation inspires one to acquire new knowledge and skills; and increase the self-competence i.e. highly valued in all human societies. In our Indian educational system deliberate attempt need, be made by the personnel concerned with it for increasing the motivational level of the sport students. It is highly essential to detect the potentialities of each sport student and to provide opportunity for their development. Since our educational set up lack necessary facilities in this regard hence the teachers concerned need be very much creative and try to ignite the thought process of each sport student as per their potentialities with the limited resources

available with them. The youth masses run with full of energy and innovative thoughts which simply need a proper direction otherwise they get wayward and the society has to pay a lot for that. In this context, the motivational state of sport students needs be set in the right perspective irrespective of the potential difference caused by gender.

Sex Differences in Sports Motivation:

Many studies outside the domain of sports have reported sex differences in motivation, including competitiveness, responses to competition, and risk-taking, a correlate of competitiveness (Croson & Gneezy, 2009; Wilson & Daly, 1985). It is not surprising, therefore, that researchers have also tested for such sex differences within sports settings. Apparently, however, there has been no previous attempt to summarize this research.

Review of Literature:

Chaturvedi (2009) found that there is significant relationship between school environment and need-achievement of children. Similarly, Navaratnam and Rao (2007) designed a study to see the difference between adolescent boys and girls on achievement motivation. They found that there was no significant difference between boys and girls with regard to achievement motivation level.

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Kaushik & Rani (2005) and Singh, V, R (2014) also confirmed the findings that there was no significant gender difference on achievement motivation in students of four educational streams. In comparing gender differences in different subjects at the university level, a study conducted by Narayanan, Rajasekaran, and Iyyappan (2007) found that in learning English, girls have greater intrinsic motivation compared (Sadaf Naz, Syed Afzal Shah and Anjum Qayum) to boys. Similarly, another research study reported higher intrinsic motivation in physical education among females as compare to males (Shang, 1998). Schatt (2011) found that female students perform better in Instrumental musical practice in the subject of music that significantly correlated with their intrinsic motivational beliefs than males. According to Conti, Collins, and Picariello, (2001) and Burger, Dahlgren, and MacDonald (2006), male students are inclined towards higher intrinsic motivation in competition and gamble than their female counterparts. S. Pany, (2014) study were based on comparison of the achievement motivation of the college students having gender, stream i.e. arts vs. science and locale i.e. urban vs. rural background. The study reported that there exists significant difference in the achievement motivation of male vs.

female, arts vs. science and urban vs. rural college students.

A good number of research studies conducted in the area of achievement motivation reveal that arts and science college students differ significantly in relation to their achievement motivation but the research studies of Arti (2007) reveal that there exists significant difference among boys and girls on the variables of achievement motivation. Poonam (2008) reveal that the girls are having higher degree of achievement motivation in comparison to boys. So in order to understand the achievement motivation of sport students with respect to gender especially the investigator decided to conduct a research of the present topic.

Objectives:

1. To measure Achievement motivation of male and female sport students.
2. To Compare Achievement Motivation between Male and Female sport students.

Hypothesis:

1. There will be significant difference in Achievement Motivation between Male and Female sport students.

Methodology:

The research method of the study was descriptive survey in nature. The present study focuses on studying the achievement motivation of college students in relation to their gender.

Sample: The sample for the present study was 60-60 players of male and female sport students who had participated at inter-university level. The age of the subjects was ranged from 16-21 years. Sample is taken from various colleges of Ahmednagar city.

Tool and Techniques:

Sports Achievement Motivation test designed by Kamlesh (1990) was used to collect the data. Test consisted of 20 incomplete statements which were to be completed by choosing either of the two proposed parts against each statement. On the basis of percentile points norms as suggested in the test those with scores below or equal 24 were categorized as low, within 25 -29 were moderate and those with 30 and above scores were categorized as high in sport achievement motivation. Descriptive statistics was used to analyze the data.

Procedure: The players were contacted individually at the competition venues through their managers and coaches and were requested to give their candid

response for understanding their actual level of motivation for making effective coaching plans.

with the help of SPSS 21 Software The obtained data were analysed by applying t test in order to determine the achievement motivation of players. To check level of

Table 1: Mean difference of Achievement Motivation between male and female Sport Students.						
	Gender	N	Mean	Std. Deviation	df	t
Achievement	Boys	60	20.52	6.212	118	1.839
	Girls	60	18.55	5.482		

Data Collection and Ethical Considerations:

Data were collected personally by the researcher. As part of the ethical considerations data were collected after seeking informed consent of the participants. Participants were ensured of anonymity and confidentiality. Participation was voluntary and questionnaires were filled during a planned time. Before the administration of the tools, the nature of the data and the purpose of research were discussed with the concerned Principals of the Colleges and the sample population. Then the tool was administered.

Statistical Method:

After the administration of the tool to the selected samples the scoring was done strictly in accordance with the directions in the tool's manual. The collected data was statistically analysed through Mean, Std. D., t-test, ANOVA

significance and to obtaining reliable result special statistics software (SPSS) was used.

Table No.1: Results and Discussion

Table 1. Shows that 't' value (1.839). The mean score of male sport students is more than the female sport students in their achievement motivation. The mean of achievement motivation of male sport student (20.52) is higher than the female sport students (18.55), which is not the significant difference at 0.05 level. It means that there is no significance difference between male and female sport students in Achievement Motivation. It was also hypothesized that "There would be no significant difference in achievement motivation between handball male and female sport students.." formulated earlier was not accepted. The significant difference was not observed in achievement motivation of male and

female sport students.. Therefore, the null hypothesis saying that

“There is significant difference in achievement motivation of male and female players.” Is not accepted. This is also supported by Shekhar, C. & Devi, R. 2012.

Several researches like Navaratnam & Rao (2007) and Kaushik and Rani (2005) found no significant difference in levels of achievement between boys and girls.

Conclusion:

“There is no significant difference in achievement motivation of male and female players.”

Achievement motivation (Need-achievement) is considered as a prerequisite for success in academic as well in other fields. As a learned motive it can be fostered among our children. The responsibility lies on the parents at home and on the teachers in the school. AS a player male and female have same roles and responsibilities. An attempt was made in this paper to analyse the players achievement motivation level along with gender. Findings reported that male and female players are same at the level of achievement motivation.

Implications of the Findings:

Educational Implications of the Study On the basis of the findings of the

study the following educational implications can be derived;

1. The sport students should be encouraged so that they can have higher degree of motivation to achieve something and to win.
2. The proper motivation should be provided to the students irrespective of gender so as to set realistic goals and attain them.
3. Home, college and society members should make their contribution equally in the development of achievement motivation among students irrespective of discrimination.
4. Proper environment on playground should be provided to the child for developing achievement directed behaviour.

Limitations:

1. The sample was selected from Ahmednagar city and district only.
2. The sample size was limited (120) for the study.

Suggestions:

1. Extensive research can be done on the presented subject by taking a large sample.
2. This research can be done using other tests for the presented research

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